

A GREEK ORTHODOX SPECIAL RELIGIOUS EDUCATION CURRICULUM

K to 7

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The views expressed are those of the author and not necessarily those of the Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of Australia or the Pantanassa Monastery. An earlier version was presented at the Australian Association for Religious Education Conference, Melbourne, September 2014.

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A GREEK ORTHODOX SPECIAL RELIGIOUS EDUCATION CURRICULUM

Introduction

The special religious education program of the Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of Australia is a major commitment by the Church to the State schools throughout New South Wales. It embodies a unique program of formal and informal learning. Although it is only one small part of the K-6 curriculum, its educational, social and spiritual effects are much broader.

To its credit, the State education system of New South Wales has fostered this community education program for over a hundred years. It is an exemplary and voluntary contribution by multi-faith providers to the State. It serves as an outstanding example of tolerance that should be the envy of the world.

The flexibility of this program is such that it has easily accommodated the faiths of immigrant groups and given them equal rights within a secular (i.e., non-denominational) system of instruction. Provision for special religious education also allows for the fact that some students have no religion or that some may desire instruction in secular ethics classes.

Although special religious education occurs within schools it is unlike most other components of the everyday curriculum. There is a natural tendency to judge it in the same way as other subject areas, such as mathematics, science, English or citizenship. Even a cursory examination shows that this program cannot be compared readily with other subject areas in terms of content, aim or even delivery. Mainstream instruction in K-6 - let alone high school - has vastly different cognitive, conative and affective pathways.

Even the small component of general religious education that is offered in some schools differs in its content, aim and delivery. This is because it offers a world-view of religion in society.

Special religious education is essentially a form of confessional teaching. Unlike most other curriculum components, participation is elective. Instruction is provided freely. There is no formal evaluation of students in this field. There is no Statewide program of assessment as in the key learning areas. It is an example of lifelong learning that commences from the earliest years. The program involves a curriculum in which experiences are repeated but with increasing levels of sophistication.

The purpose of this document is to provide a brief outline of the curriculum for Greek Orthodox special religious education. It sets out in simple terms the content of the curriculum and offers an initial educational justification.

It is not intended to replicate the format or style of other curriculum documents for school subjects that are examinable. It does, however, provide information on educational aims, the developmental sequence and the curriculum structure. This is intended primarily for use by those involved in special religious education.

This Special Religious Education Curriculum is regarded as a work in progress that will be updated annually and revised to take into account developments in religious education. This outline of the Greek Orthodox Special Religious Education curriculum commences with a brief consideration of the goals.

The overarching goal of the special religious education program is the welfare of the child. This is paramount to the Greek Orthodox Archdiocese. This holistic aim is analysed under three broad headings: educational, social and spiritual goals.

Four broad educational goals of special religious education

The educational purpose is to provide a coherent and structured introduction to the Orthodox Christian faith. This introduction is presented in a way that respects the cognitive, conative and affective capacity of the child.

It is easy to assume that the goals of special religious education relate to ethical behaviour or biblical knowledge. This is a vast simplification of religion. Actually these can be one of the by-products of a Greek Orthodox special religious education.

The purpose is not to proselytise. This is because those attending special religious education are already Orthodox.

Four broad educational key goals are:

- To support the educational aims of public education for Orthodox Christian students;
- To complement the existing curriculum with specific knowledge, skills or attitudes;
- To provide instruction in a specialised area (i.e., related to the Greek Orthodox faith); and
- To develop interest in religion as a discipline or field of study in its own right.

For these reasons special religious education is considered as a partnership between the home, the school and one's faith. The extent of overlap (if any) will vary from case to case and in a sense it is the goal of special religious education to ensure that this potential is harnessed.

Figure 1. The symbolic partnership between school, student, home and faith

Five broad social goals of special religious education

The five broad social goals of Greek Orthodox special religious education enhance the social capital of the community. In brief - and without much further comment – they are:

- To promote the individual freedom of the child;
- To create an attitude of religious tolerance in the school;
- To accept everyone of all faiths;
- To reinforce the human right to religion; and
- To establish religiousness as an aspect of positive citizenship.

Five broad spiritual goals of special religious education

The Greek Orthodox special religious education program is distinctively spiritual. It acknowledges the spiritual dimension in life. If one were to take away the educational and social goals this aspect alone still justifies the provision of special religious education.

For reasons that are obvious the spiritual goals of education are not conveyed in the formal, day-to-day curriculum of the multi-faith classroom. This is understandable and accepted.

At the same time it is equally important for others to accept that many Australians acknowledge a faith and most accept that there is a religious dimension to life. It is irrational to exclude this aspect from schooling. It cannot be divorced from the totality of a child's life.

Despite the importance of spirituality it is not easy for most families to provide a comprehensive or systematic religious education in the home in the same way as it is often difficult for them to provide specialised instruction in music or sport or coaching in some subjects. They can provide an introduction and some assistance but of necessity it is incomplete and often fragmented.

From K-7 Greek Orthodox special religious education offers an organised and integrated program of spiritual development that complements the family's teaching.

Understandably the Greek Orthodox special religious education program seeks to complement the secular instruction of the school in a unique way.

Five broad religious or spiritual goals of Greek Orthodox special religious education are listed below. These are:

- To establish the importance of the human soul;
- To recognise that life is a great gift;
- To promote the happiness of the child;
- To foster the value of a religious outlook on life; and
- To encourage a sacramental life in children.

These spiritual goals are timeless. They are considered paramount in the day-to-day Orthodox special religious education of children in New South Wales.

The relative importance of educational, social and spiritual goals across the curriculum

The relative importance of the goals across the curriculum was investigated to determine their influence.

A classification of the 299 units in these courses from Kindergarten to Year 7 was undertaken by the author. Of necessity it is subjective and has not been validated. The details are provided in Appendix C. In some instances topics of the units overlap with more than one goal but only the main focus was categorised. The results are summarised in Figure 2.

At this point in time it appears that there is a primary educational emphasis on Orthodox religion and faith and this is followed by a spiritual emphasis. The ethical and moral prescriptions of the Orthodox faith were not as prominent as the educational component of special religious education.

Figure 2. Distribution of topics across special religious education goals

The syllabus

The special religious education syllabus of the Greek Orthodox Archdiocese was developed over a period of some 30 years. It has been reviewed continuously throughout that period and major improvements undertaken to ensure that it meets the developmental needs of children. By and large it has stood the test of time. No claim is made that it is perfect.

Some features of the curriculum that are worthy of attention are noted in the paragraphs that follow. In summary these are:

- The program offers an educational scaffold for learners
- The program is multivariate in content
- The content of the units is timeless in its relevance
- The topic of each unit is applicable to people of all ages

- The program is descriptive
- The content of the units allows for increases in complexity across the ages

Nevertheless it provides an educational scaffold for the delivery of special religious education. It sets out a series of topics and content to be followed throughout K-7. If this program is completed in its entirety it would provide a comprehensive special religious education.

As it stands the current curriculum is multivariate in content. It covers a variety of topics. It is flexible enough to be able to be adjusted so that some lessons can be brought forward to coincide with religious occasions. There is provision for additional lessons if required for feasts such as that of a patron saint.

In one sense the curriculum does not deal with current affairs, political issues or problems in society (e.g., drug abuse, poverty, oppression, wars). These are considered to fall within the ambit of other disciplines in the school curriculum.

In a very real way, this curriculum is intended to be timeless. With minor exceptions its content was as valid some 200 years ago as it will be in some 200 years into the future. In its essence it is unchanging.

There is another aspect of this curriculum that may be difficult to grasp at first glance, namely, the content of the units is actually applicable to people of all ages. For instance very topic in the Infants Stage 1 or the Primary Stage 1 is as applicable to adults as it is to these age groups (see Appendix A for a listing of topics). This underlies the universality of special religious education and its importance for human development.

Overall, this curriculum is more descriptive than prescriptive. It outlines the content and the sequence but does not specify how it should be taught. This aspect is really a matter for the classroom teacher or catechist. The lesson and its delivery will be adapted to the personality of the class. It will vary according to the background, experience and ability of the learners. It will be dependent upon the teaching context. Some guidance is provided but ultimately it must suit the situation and the developmental needs of the learners.

Worksheets are provided for each lesson but the use of these is not mandated. Lesson summaries with background material, objectives, questions and outcomes have been prepared but this is only a starting point.

The current curriculum evolved from a thematic program that dealt with specific topics, such as the Feasts of the Church or the Sacraments in some depth. It was comprehensive and a major improvement on earlier ad hoc programs.

In response to a request from teachers a mixed curriculum was developed that integrated the themes. This covered the same topics but with greater variety. It provided a developmental sequence from K-7. Overall, it is linked to the educational concepts of Bruner, namely "...that any

subject can be taught effectively in some intellectually honest form to any child at any stage of development”¹.

Figure 3. The spiral curriculum

The mixed themes were consistent with the idea of a spiral curriculum (see Figure 3). Different aspects of a topic were encountered throughout K-7 but with greater complexity as the years progressed. It was also consistent with teaching in classes of mixed grades where aspects of a lesson could be pitched to different cognitive levels.

In this spiral curriculum the sacraments will be encountered in Kindergarten and in each grade right through to Year 6 and beyond. The teaching of the earlier stages is reinforced according to (a) the intellectual development of the learner; (b) their background and experience; and (c) their spiritual maturity.

Units of work

The infants program comprises 111 units over three years. The title or content of each unit is provided in Appendix A. The primary program contains 149 units over a four-year period. These details are also listed in Appendix A.

A concrete expression of each unit of work is shown by the 260 separate worksheets for infants and primary grades. These are written in English on one side and Greek on the other and have been

¹ Bruner, J (1960). *The Process of Education*, Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard University Press, p. 33.

prepared by the Pantanassa Monastery². A sample of the first worksheet from the Infants Stage 1 is provided in Figure 4. Copies of these worksheets are freely available at <http://www.pantanassamonastery.org> As an example of its application within a yearly program, Appendix B provides the schedule of teaching for 2014.

Figure 4. A unit from the Infants Stage 1 program

Indicative time

The indicative time for special religious education typically averages at around 30 minutes per week.

Content

The curriculum content is comprehensive and ranges across seven major categories:

- Church (includes history of the church, vestments of the priest)
- Worship (includes the Divine Liturgy, prayers)
- Saints
- Our behaviour
- Feasts
- Christ (includes the life of Christ, parables and events in the New Testament)

² The cooperation and support of the Pantanassa Monastery in making available these curriculum materials freely and revising them in 2013 is gratefully acknowledged. Work on this curriculum has been ongoing over a period of some 30 years. The assistance of Mrs Helen Magdas in assembling the original mixed curriculum is also gratefully acknowledged.

- Old testament

This classification is also subjective and has not been verified independently. There are some units that could easily be classified under more than one category. This applies in particular to lessons relating to Christ; these have multiple features.

The results are summarised in Figure 5 (see Appendix C for the tabulations). There is an emphasis on topics related to the Saints, Christ, Old Testament and Church. Again it is clear that the emphasis is on religious content that is not readily available elsewhere in the school; moral instruction (e.g., ethics) is not the key theme of this Orthodox program of special religious education.

Figure 5. Distribution of units across content areas

Aims, conclusions and questions

Each lesson is designed with specific aims in mind. It is accompanied by some sample questions for each unit. There is also a short statement of the conclusions as a guide for the instructor.

Aims

The aims set the purpose of the unit for the teacher. It is the driver for the teaching and learning that will occur in the unit. Ideally they reflect the broad educational, social and spiritual goals of special religious education in one form or another.

The number of outcomes is restricted to a manageable number (usually 2-3). They are not intended to be complex behavioural objectives or competencies.

A set of outcomes for a typical lesson is shown in Figure 6.

THE BLESSING OF WATER IN OUR HOME
<u><i>Aim of the lesson:</i></u>
a) That the children realise that for each major event in our life we should ask for God's blessing.
b) To understand that through the Blessing of Water we receive Grace and God's blessing.

Figure 6. A typical statement of aims for a religious lesson

Questions

Sample questions are provided with each unit to assist the teacher. A typical set of questions is listed in Figure 7. These are based on the previous lesson, as in Figure 6.

<u><i>Questions</i></u>
1. How is the Megas Agiasmos done?
2. How is the Mikros Agiasmos done?
3. How do we keep the blessed water in our homes, when do we drink from it, and with what preparation?
4. How do we participate in the service of the Blessing of the Water, in order to receive the blessing of God?

Figure 7. A typical sample of questions for a religious lesson

Conclusion

The key message from each lesson is summarised for the teacher in the conclusion. A further example from the same lesson is provided in Figure 8. The wording is not intended as a script for the teacher but rather as a guide to the meaning of the lesson and as a basis for consolidating knowledge.

<u><i>Conclusion</i></u>
In each significant, and in every new event in our lives, but also in every difficult moment, it is necessary to ask for God's help. The Grace of God is given with the Blessing of the Water to us, and to our homes. When we have a certain need, we should participate in the Blessing of the Water with faith and prayerfully, and then the Grace of God enters into our life.

Figure 8. A typical statement of aims for a religious lesson

Other aspects of the special religious education program: chanting, craft, prayer and use of technology

A common perception of religious instruction is that it is largely didactic, teacher-based and passive. This is as stereotyped a view of religious instruction as it is of modern teaching in schools.

The unit outlines indicate the topics that will be covered throughout the year but do not portray the variety of activities that make up each lesson. The choice of activities is the responsibility of the teacher and takes into account all the factors and variables that are operating in each classroom situation.

There are other aspects of teaching that are not widely recognised within the Greek Orthodox special religious education program. These include: chanting, craft, prayer and use of technology (where available).

An example of a simple craft activity is illustrated in Figure 9. A program of chanting is specified for each grade and this is summarised in Appendix D.

Figure 9. A simple craft activity to accompany a lesson

Assessment and evaluation in the special religious education curriculum

The Greek Orthodox special religious education program is not an examinable subject in New South Wales schools. Accordingly, no summative assessment is undertaken. No formal assessment is prescribed within this curriculum because it is inconsistent with the philosophy of special religious education. Special religious education is not like the other school subjects.

Notwithstanding the voluntary and participative emphasis, there will always be a component of formative assessment on the part of the teacher. This formative assessment occurs mainly through

questioning and samples of work undertaken in class. It will determine the direction, pace and sequence of instruction so that it is geared to the needs of learners.

An equally important aspect is the ongoing and overall evaluation of the special religious education curriculum. This involves the systematic investigation of the merit or worth of the curriculum. To date this has been informal, largely in response to the resources available but also because of the flexibility and adaptability of informal evaluations.

Ultimately any evaluation of the curriculum would need to be undertaken in the context of an ongoing review of the special religious education program in its entirety. In other contexts the author has recommended that educational evaluations have regard for six key features: (a) the ethics and morality of the curriculum, (b) its human, economic, resource, social, educational, and spiritual costs, (c) the coverage of the program, (d) the extent to which the objectives are achieved, (e) the direct and indirect effects and (f) the extent to which it meets the needs of all stakeholders. Only when this information is combined can some judgement be made about the merit or worth of the curriculum.

Concluding remarks

The special religious education program of the Greek orthodox Archdiocese centres upon the curriculum outlined in this document. It is both a straightforward outline of the teaching from K-6 but also involves a complex educational rationale. In a very real sense the educational rationale has followed the implementation. It has been grounded in practice and as such has many theoretical benefits that would not otherwise have been available.

In summary, this program covers 299 units from K-7 within a spiral curriculum. It addresses three overarching goals that are educational, social and spiritual in nature. The content deals with seven main topic areas: Church, worship, saints, our behaviour, feasts, Christ and the Old Testament. The curriculum is supported by teaching material in the form of worksheets and lesson notes for teachers that outline the aims, content, key questions and conclusion for each unit. This formal curriculum has evolved over a period of some 30 years.

APPENDIX A: AN OUTLINE OF THE MIXED THEMES CURRICULUM BY GRADE AND YEAR

INFANTS STAGE 1 (previously Kindergarten)

Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of Australia

 Pentecost Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W.

1. Agiasmos in our homes
2. Saint Philothea
3. Do not say Lies
4. Sunday of Orthodoxy
5. All the Children of the World
6. On Sunday we go to Church
7. Our Hymn to Panagia
8. The Last Supper
9. Easter
10. My Name Day
11. Adam and Eve
12. Honour your Father and Mother
13. Moses
14. The Holy Liturgy
15. The Feast Day of our Parish
16. Do not Steal
17. The Holy Vestments
18. The Birth of St John the Baptist
19. St Peter and Paul
20. The Prophoro
21. Saint Panteleimon
22. Do not be Jealous
23. Panagia
24. God Calls Samuel
25. Our Prayer Before a Meal
26. David and Goliath
27. Keep Sunday Holy
28. My Grandfather
29. The Holy Cross
30. The Monastery
31. Esther
32. The Forty-Day Blessing
33. Zacchaeus
34. The Holy Bible
35. St Nectarios
36. Saint Katherine
37. The Three Wise Men

INFANTS STAGE 2 (previously Year 1)

Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of Australia

*Pantanama Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. Agiasmos at School
2. Saint Haralambos
3. The Lord's Prayer
4. Our Lord Jesus and Children
5. Icons
6. God's Beautiful World
7. The Archangel Visits Maria
8. Sunday School Begins
9. Our Father in Heaven
10. Easter
11. Saint George
12. Mother's Day
13. Joseph and his Brothers
14. Making the Sign of the Cross
15. Hallowed be Your Name..
16. Our Church
17. Thankyou
18. Noah's Ark
19. St Peter
20. Our Priest
21. Your Will Be Done..
22. Joachim and Anna
23. A Sick Little Girl
24. Fasting
25. Panagia
26. Give us this Day..
27. David the Shepherd Boy
28. My Father
29. Cross
30. Saint Sophia and her Three Daughters
31. Praying to God
32. And Forgive us our Sins..
33. Daniel
34. Saint Demetrios
35. Our Archbishop
36. Our Guardian Angel
37. And Lead us not into Temptation..

INFANTS STAGE 3 (previously Year 2)

Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of Australia

"Pantassina" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. Jesus is Baptised
2. The Sacrament of Baptism
3. In God's House
4. Holy Confession
5. Sunday School
6. The Angel and Maria
7. Great Lent
8. Icons Help us to Pray
9. The Holy Cross
10. Jonah
11. Easter
12. Our Grandmother
13. Abraham
14. Saint Helen
15. Jesus is our Friend
16. The Blind Man
17. Holy Chrism
18. Pentecost
19. All Saints
20. Jacob
21. God is Everywhere
22. Holy Communion
23. The Feast of the Mother of God
24. The Ten Commandments
25. Saint Kosmas Aitolos
26. God's Gifts
27. Our Priest
28. Prayer
29. Ruth
30. St Luke and the Holy Bible
31. Marriage
32. St Kosmas and Damianos
33. The Archangels - My Angel
34. The Good Samaritan
35. Holy Unction
36. The Sacraments
37. When our Lord Jesus was Born

"Pantanassa" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

PRIMARY STAGE 1 (previously Year 3)

1. The Four Gospels
2. Jesus and the Woman from Canaan
3. The Pharisee and the Tax Collector
4. The Parable of the Prodigal Son
5. Icons and the Great Council
6. The Angel Visits Maria
7. Palm Sunday
8. Holy Week
9. The Last Supper
10. The Resurrection of our Lord Jesus
11. God's Plan
12. A Man Healed at the Pool of Bethesda
13. Saint Constantine
14. The Ascension of our Lord Jesus
15. Pentecost
16. The First Church
17. Saint Peter and Paul
18. Paul in Rome
19. The Sermon on the Mount
20. Parable of the Good Samaritan
21. Jesus Heals and Forgives a Paralytic
22. The Persecution of Christians
23. Jesus is Transfigured
24. The Dormition of the Theotokos
25. A Boy is Healed
26. The Death of John the Baptist
27. Jesus Heals Jairus's Daughter
28. The Feast of the Holy Cross
29. The Monasteries
30. The First Disciples
31. Jesus Heals a Man Born Blind
32. Our Priests
33. Saint James the Brother of our Lord
34. Saint Demetrios
35. The Rich Man and Lazarus
36. Water Turned into Wine
37. The Church in Australia
38. The Birth of our Lord Jesus
39. The Baptism of our Lord Jesus

PRIMARY STAGE 2 (previously Year 4)

Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of Australia

"Pantanassa" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. The Three Hierarchs
2. The Ten Lepers
3. Holy Confession
4. The Second Coming
5. Satan Tempts the Lord Jesus
6. The Church during Turkish Rule
7. The Parable of the Ten Maidens
8. Good Friday
9. Easter
10. The Parable of the Great Feast
11. The Rich Young Man
12. The Parable of the Mustard Seed
13. The Apostle Peter
14. The Apostle Paul
15. God Cares for Us
16. Paul's First Journey
17. Paul in Greece
18. Paul's Third Journey
19. The Transfiguration
20. Panagia
21. St John the Evangelist
22. The First Martyr
23. Saint John the Baptist
24. The Age of Martyrs
25. Elevation of the Holy Cross
26. The Centurion's Servant
27. The New Martyrs
28. The First Disciples are Called
29. Jesus Walks on Water
30. The Parable of the Sower
31. Orthodox Mission
32. The Feeding of the Five Thousand
33. Priesthood
34. The Bishop
35. Jesus Straightens the Bowed Woman
36. The Shepherds
37. The Three Wise Men

PRIMARY STAGE 3 (previously Year 5)

Greek Orthodox Archdiocese of Australia

"Pantanassa" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. God Creates the World
2. Sunday of Meat-Fare
3. Great Lent
4. The Deacon's vestments
5. Adam and Eve are Punished
6. Give us this Day our Daily Bread
7. The Holy Liturgy
8. Holy Week
9. The Resurrection
10. Sunday of the Apostle Thomas
11. Jacob and Esau
12. But Deliver us from Evil
13. The Weekly Cycle
14. Joseph Sold by his Brothers
15. The Ascension
16. Thy Kingdom Come
17. Sunday of All Saints
18. The Holy Apostles
19. Saint Marina
20. The Parable of the Good Shepherd
21. The Story of Ruth
22. The Transfiguration
23. Panagia
24. Samuel
24. Saint John the Baptist
25. The Holy Liturgy
26. David and Goliath
27. David the King
28. The Holy Liturgy
29. Saint Gerasimos
30. Saint Demetrios
31. The Angels and the Devil
32. Solomon
33. Saint Katherine
34. The Holy Liturgy- The Holy Offering
35. The Prophet Isaiah
36. The Birth of our Lord Jesus Christ

PRIMARY STAGE 4 (previously Year 6)

"Pantanassa" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. The Ten Lepers
2. The Triodion
3. As we forgive those who sin against us..
4. The Six Days of Creation
5. The Holy Liturgy-Sunday
6. Third, Fourth, Fifth Sunday of Lent
7. The Parable of the Talents
8. Holy Wednesday, Thursday, Friday
9. Christ is Risen
10. Adam and Eve in Paradise
11. The Paralytic,
12. The Vestments of the Priest
13. The Tower of Babel
14. The Twelve Disciples
15. Pentecost
16. For Thine is the Kingdom
17. The Patriarch Abraham
18. St Christina, Paraskevi,Panteleimon
19. Moses is Born
20. God Calls Moses
21. The Transfiguration
22. The Dormition
23. The Holy Liturgy - The Small Entrance
24. The Ten Plagues
25. The Parable of the Wheat and Tares
26. The Holy Liturgy - Great Entrance
27. The Parable of the Unforgiving Servant
28. The Crossing of the Red Sea
29. Saint Luke
30. The Ten Commandment
31. Saint Kosmas and Damianos
32. The Golden Calf
33. The Vestments of the Bishop
34. Saint Andrew
35. The Holy Liturgy -The Holy Gifts
36. The Death of Moses
37. Christmas

**Themes for High School
The Divine Liturgy**

"Pantanassa" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. Introduction to the Holy Liturgy
2. Sunday
3. The Preparation by the Priest
4. The Service of Prothesis or Proskomidi
5. The Meaning of the Proskomidi
6. The Doxology
7. In Peace let us Pray
8. The Small Entrance
9. The Trisagion Hymn
10. The Gospel Reading
11. The Great Entrance
12. The Prayers after the Great Entrance
13. The Confession of our Faith
14. The Holy Offering
15. The Holy Offering continued
16. Holy Communion

**Themes for High School
History of the Church**

“Pantanassa” Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. The First Church
2. The Apostle Paul
3. Paul’s First Journey
4. Paul’s Second Journey
5. Paul in Greece
6. Paul’s Third Journey
7. Paul in Rome
8. Paul’s Fourth Journey
9. The Apostle Peter
10. The Persecution of Christians
11. The Age of Martyrs
12. Saint Constantine
13. The First Ecumenical Council
14. The Second-Sixth Council
15. Icons and the Seventh Council
16. The Three Heirarchs
17. Monasticism
18. The Conversion of the Slavs
19. The Great Schism
20. The Reformation
21. The Church During Turkish Rule
22. The New Martyrs
23. The Church in Asia Minor
24. The Greek Orthodox Church in
Australia

Themes for High School
The Lord's Prayer

"Pantanassa" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. Our Father
2. Who is in Heaven
3. Hallowed be you name
4. Your Kingdom Come
5. Your Will be done on earth as
it is in heaven
6. Give us this day our daily
bread
7. And forgive us our sins
8. As we forgive those who sin
against us
9. And lead us not into
temptation
10. But deliver us from evil
11. For Your's is the Kingdom, the
power and the glory of the
Father and the Son and the
Holy Spirit. Amen

**Themes for High School
Holy Vestments**

"Pantanassa" Greek Orthodox Monastery, N.S.W

1. The Clergy - An Introduction
2. The Clergy - Continued
3. The Holy Vestments of the Deacon
4. The Holy Vestments of the Priest
5. The Holy Vestments of the Bishop
6. The Bishop in our Church

APPENDIX B: A SAMPLE PROGRAM OF WORK FOR 2014

MY 2014 INFANTS STAGE 1 SCRIPTURE PROGRAM AND CALENDAR

Week	Dates	Unit
1		Agiasmos in our homes
2	February 19	Saint Philothei
3		Do not say lies
4	March 9	Sunday of Orthodoxy
5		All the children of the world
6		On Sunday we go to church
7	March 25	Our hymn to Panagia
8	April 13	The Last Supper
9	April 20	Easter
10		My name day
11		Adam and Eve
12		Honour your father and mother
13		Moses
14		The Holy Liturgy
15		The feast day of our parish
16		Do not steal
17		The holy vestments
18	June 24	The birth of St John the Baptist
19	June 29	Sts Peter and Paul
20		The Proshphoro
21	July 27	Saint Panteleimon
22		Do not be jealous
23	August 15	Panagia
24		God calls Samuel
25		Our prayer before a meal
26		David and Goliath
27		Keep Sunday holy
28		My grandfather
29	September 14	The Holy Cross
30		The Monastery
31		Esther
32		The Forty-day Blessing
33		Zacchaeus
34		The Holy Bible
35	November 9	St Nectarios
36	November 25	Saint Katherine
37	December 25	The Three Wise Men

LITURGICAL CALENDAR 2014 – to be included in the program where relevant

February 9	Triodion begins	June 15	All Saints
March 3	Lent Begins	August 6	Transfiguration of the Lord
March 25	Annunciation of the Theotokos	August 15	Dormition of the Theotokos
March 9	Sunday of Orthodoxy	September 8	Nativity of the Theotokos
April 20	Western Easter	September 14	Elevation of the Holy Cross
April 13	Palm Sunday	November 21	Entrance of the Theotokos into the Temple
April 20	Great and Holy Pascha	December 25	Nativity of the Lord
May 29	Ascension of the Lord	January 6	Theophany
June 8	Pentecost		

MY 2014 PRIMARY SCHOOL STAGE 1 SCRIPTURE PROGRAM AND CALENDAR

Week	Approximate Dates	Unit
1		The Four Gospels
2		Jesus and the Woman from Canaan
3		The Pharisee and the Tax Collector
4		The Parable of the Prodigal son
5	March 9	Icons and the Great Council
6	March 25	The Angel visits Maria
7	April 13	Palm Sunday
8		Holy Week
9		The Last Supper
10	April 20	The Resurrection of our Lord Jesus
11		God's plan
12		A man healed at the Pool of Bethesda
13	May 21	Saint Constantine
14	May 29	The Ascension of our Lord Jesus
15	June 8	Pentecost
16		The first Church
17	June 29	Saints Peter and Paul
18		Paul in Rome
19		The Sermon on the Mount
20		Parable of the Good Samaritan
21		Jesus heals and forgives a Paralytic
22		The persecution of Christians
23	August 6	Jesus is Transfigured
24	August 15	The Dormition of the Theotokos
25		A boy is healed
26	August 29	The death of John the Baptist
27		Jesus heals Jairus's daughter
28	September 14	The Feast of the Holy Cross
29		The Monasteries
30		The first disciples
31		Jesus heals a man born blind
32		Our priests
33	October 23	Saint James the Brother of Our Lord
34	October 26	Saint Demetrios
35		The Rich Man and Lazarus
36		Water turned into wine
37		The Church in Australia
38	December 25	The Birth of Our Lord Jesus
39	January 6	The Baptism of Our Lord Jesus

LITURGICAL CALENDAR 2014 – to be included in the program where relevant

February 9	Triodion begins	June 15	All Saints
March 3	Lent Begins	August 6	Transfiguration of the Lord
March 25	Annunciation of the Theotokos	August 15	Dormition of the Theotokos
March 9	Sunday of Orthodoxy	September 8	Nativity of the Theotokos
April 20	Western Easter	September 14	Elevation of the Holy Cross
April 13	Palm Sunday	November 21	Entrance of the Theotokos into the Temple
April 20	Great and Holy Pascha	December 25	Nativity of the Lord
May 29	Ascension of the Lord	January 6	Theophany
June 8	Pentecost		

APPENDIX C: A CLASSIFICATION OF UNITS

(a) Infants Stage 1

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
1. Agiasmos in our homes			1	1						
2. Saint Philothea	1					1				
3. Do not say Lies		1					1			
4. Sunday of Orthodoxy			1					1		
5. All the Children of the World		1					1			
6. On Sunday we go to Church			1		1					
7. Our Hymn to Panaygia			1		1					
8. The Last Supper			1						1	
9. Easter			1						1	
10. My Name Day		1						1		
11. Adam and Eve	1									1
12. Honour your Father and Mother		1					1			
13. Moses			1							1
14. The Holy Liturgy			1		1					
15. The Feast Day of our Parish	1							1		
16. Do not Steal		1					1			
17. The Holy Vestments	1			1						
18. The Birth of St John the Baptist	1					1				
19. St Peter and Paul	1					1				
20. The Prosporo	1			1						
21. Saint Panteleimon	1					1				
22. Do not be Jealous		1					1			
23. Panagia	1					1				
24. God Calls Samuel			1							1
25. Our Prayer Before a Meal			1		1					

26. David and Goliath	1									1
27. Keep Sunday Holy			1	1						
28. My Grandfather		1					1			
29. The Holy Cross	1							1		
30. The Monastery	1			1						
31. Esther	1									1
32. The Forty-Day Blessing	1			1						
33. Zacchaeus	1								1	
34. The Holy Bible	1				1					
35. StNectarios	1					1				
36. Saint Katherine	1					1				
37. The Three Wise Men	1								1	
Total	19	7	11	6	5	7	6	4	4	5

(b) Infants Stage 2

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
1. Agiasmos at School			1	1						
2. Saint Haralambos	1					1				
3. The Lord's Prayer			1		1					
4. Our Lord Jesus and Children		1							1	
5. Icons			1	1						
6. God's Beautiful World		1					1			
7. The Archangel Visits Maria	1					1				
8. Sunday School Begins		1					1			
9. Our Father in Heaven			1		1					
10. Easter			1						1	
11. Saint George	1					1				
12. Mother's Day		1					1			

13. Joseph and his Brothers	1									1
14. Making the Sign of the Cross			1		1					
15. Hallowed be Your Name			1		1					
16. Our Church			1	1						
17. Thank You		1					1			
18. Noah's Ark	1									1
19. St Peter	1					1				
20. Our Priest	1			1						
21. Your Will be Done			1		1					
22. Joachimn and Anna	1						1			
23. A Sick Little Girl		1							1	
24. Fasting			1		1					
25. Panagia	1						1			
26. Give us this Day			1			1				
27. David the Shepherd Boy	1									1
28. My Father		1						1		
29. Cross	1								1	
30. Saint Sohia and her Three Daughters	1						1			
31. Praying to God			1			1				
32. And Forgive us our Sins			1			1				
33. Daniel	1									1
34. Saint Demetrios	1						1			
35. Our Archbishop	1				1					
36. Our GuardianAngel			1				1			
37. And Lead us not into Temptation			1			1				
Total	15	7	15	6	9	9	5	1	3	4

(c) Infants Stage 3

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
1. Agiasmos at School			1	1						
2. Saint Haralambos	1					1				
3. The Lord's Prayer			1		1					
4. Our Lord Jesus and Children		1							1	
5. Icons			1	1						
6. God's Beautiful World		1					1			
7. The Archangel Visits Maria	1					1				
8. Sunday School Begins		1					1			
9. Our Father in Heaven			1		1					
10. Easter			1						1	
11. Saint George	1					1				
12. Mother's Day		1					1			
13. Joseph and his Brothers	1									1
14. Making the Sign of the Cross			1		1					
15. Hallowed be Your Name			1		1					
16. Our Church			1	1						
17. Thank You		1					1			
18. Noah's Ark	1									1
19. St Peter	1					1				
20. Our Priest	1			1						
21. Your Will be Done			1		1					
22. Joachimn and Anna	1					1				
23. A Sick Little Girl		1							1	
24. Fasting			1	1						
25. Panagia	1					1				
26. Give us this Day			1		1					
27. David the Shepherd Boy	1									1

28. My Father		1				1				
29. Cross	1							1		
30. Saint Sofia and her Three Daughters	1					1				
31. Praying to God				1		1				
32. And Forgive us our Sins				1		1				
33. Daniel	1									1
34. Saint Demetrios	1					1				
35. Our Archbishop	1				1					
36. Our GuardianAngel				1				1		
37. And Lead us not into Temptation				1		1				
Total	15	7	15	6	9	9	5	1	3	4

(d) Primary Stage 1

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
1. The Four Gospels	1								1	
2. Jesus and the Woman from Canaan		1							1	
3. The Pharisee and the Tax Collector		1							1	
4. The Parable of the Prodigal Son		1							1	
5. Icons and the Great Council			1	1						
6. The Angel visits Maria			1			1				
7. Palm Sunday			1		1					
8. Holy Week			1		1					
9. The Last Supper			1		1					
10. The Resurrection of our Lord Jesus			1						1	
11. God's plan			1							1
12. A man healed at the Pool of Bethesda	1								1	
13. Saint Constantine	1					1				
14. The Ascension of our Lord Jesus			1						1	

15. Pentecost			1				1			
16. The first Church		1								
17. Saints Peter and Paul	1			1		1				
18. Paul in Rome	1					1				
19. The Sermon on the Mount			1				1			
20. Parable of the Good Samaritan		1							1	
21. Jesus heals and forgives a Paralytic	1								1	
22. The persecution of Christians		1		1						
23. Jesus is Transfigured			1						1	
24. The Dormition of the Theotokos			1				1			
25. A boy is healed		1							1	
26. The death of John the Baptist			1				1			
27. Jesus heals Jairus's daughter		1							1	
28. The Feast of the Holy Cross			1				1			
29. The Monasteries		1		1						
30. The first disciples	1					1				
31. Jesus heals a man born blind		1							1	
32. Our priests			1	1						
33. Saint James the Brother of Our Lord	1					1				
34. Saint Demetrios	1					1				
35. The Rich Man and Lazarus		1							1	
36. Water turned into wine	1								1	
37. The Church in Australia		1		1						
38. The Birth of Our Lord Jesus			1						1	
39. The Baptism of Our Lord Jesus			1						1	
Total	10	12	17	6	3	7	1	4	17	1

(e) Primary Stage 2

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
1. The Three Hierarchs	1					1				
2. The Ten Lepers		1							1	
3. Holy Confession			1		1					
4. The Second Coming	1								1	
5. Satan Tempts the Lord Jesus			1						1	
6. The Church during the Turkish Rule	1			1						
7. The Parable of the Ten Maidens		1					1			
8. Good Friday			1						1	
9. Easter			1						1	
10. The Parable of the Great Feast		1					1			
11. The rich YoungMan		1					1			
12. The Parable of the Mustard Seed	1						1			
13. The Apostle Peter	1					1				
14. The Apostle Paul	1					1				
15. God Cares for us.		1					1			
16. Paul's First Journey	1					1				
17. Paul in Greece	1					1				
18. Paul's Third journey	1					1				
19. The Transfiguration			1						1	
20. Panagia	1					1				
21. St John the Evangelist	1					1				
22. The First Martyr	1					1				
23. St John the Baptist	1					1				
24. The Age of Martyrs	1					1				
25. Elevation of the Holy Cross			1					1		
26. The Centurion's Servant		1					1			
27. The New Martyrs	1					1				

28. The First Disciples are Called	1								1	
29. Jesus Walks on the Water	1								1	
30. The Parable of the Sower		1					1			
31. Orthodox Mission		1					1			
32. The Feeding of the Five Thousand	1								1	
33. Priesthood		1		1						
34. The Bishop		1		1						
35. Jesus Straightens the Bowed Woman	1								1	
36. The Shepherds	1								1	
37. The Three Wise Men	1								1	
Total	21	10	6	3	1	12	8	1	12	0

(f) Primary Stage 3

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
God Creates the World	1									1
Sunday of Meat-Fare			1					1		
Great Lent			1					1		
The Deacon's Vestments	1			1						
Adam and Eve are Punished	1									1
Give us this Day our Daily Bread			1		1					
The Holy Liturgy			1	1						
Holy Week			1					1		
The Resurrection			1						1	
Sunday of the Apostle Thomas	1					1				
Jacob and Esau	1									1
But Deliver us from Evil			1		1					
The Weekly cycle	1				1					
Joseph Sold by his Brothers	1									1

The Ascension			1					1		
Thy Kingdom Come			1		1					
Sunday of All Saints	1							1		
The Holy Apostles	1					1				
Saint Marina	1					1				
The Parable of the Good Shepherd		1					1			
The Story of Ruth	1								1	
The Transfiguration	1							1		
Panagia	1					1				
Samuel	1								1	
Saint John the Baptist	1					1				
The Holy Liturgy			1		1					
David and Goliath	1								1	
David the King	1								1	
The Holy Liturgy			1		1					
Saint Gerasimos	1					1				
Saint Demetrios	1					1				
The Angels and the Devil			1		1					
Solomon	1								1	
Saint Katherine	1					1				
The Holy Liturgy - The Holy Offering			1		1					
The Prophet Isaiah	1								1	
The Birth of Our Lord Jesus Christ	1							1		
Total	23	1	13	6	4	8	1	4	4	10

(g) Primary Stage 4

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
1. The Ten Lepers		1					1			
2. The Triodion	1				1					
3. As we forgive those who sin against us...			1		1					
4. The Six Days of Creation	1									1
5. The Holy Liturgy - Sunday			1	1						
6. Third, Fourth, Fifth Sunday of Lent	1				1					
7. The Parable of the Talents		1					1			
8. Holy Wednesday, Thursday, Friday			1		1					
9. Christ is Risen			1						1	
10. Adam and Eve in paradise	1									1
11. The Paralytic	1								1	
12. The Vestments of the Priest	1			1						
13. The Tower of Babel	1									1
14. The Twelve Disciples	1					1				
15. Pentecost			1		1			1		
16. For Thine is the Kingdom			1							
17. The Patriarch Abraham	1									1
18. St Christina, Paraskevi, Panteleimon	1					1				
19. Moses is Born	1									1
20. God Calls Moses	1									1
21. The Transfiguration	1								1	
22. The Dormition	1							1		
23. The Holy Liturgy - The Small Entrance	1			1						
24. The Ten Plagues	1									1
25. The Parable of the Wheat and the Tares	1						1			
26. The Holy Liturgy - Great Entrance	1			1						
27. The Parable of the Unforgiving Servant		1					1			

28. The Crossing of the Red Sea	1									1
29. Saint Luke	1					1				
30. The Ten Commandments	1									1
31. Saints Kosmas and Damianos	1					1				
32. The Golden Calf	1									1
33. The Vestments of the Bishop	1			1						
34. Saint Andrew	1					1				
35. The Holy Liturgy - The Holy Gifts	1			1						
36. The Death of Moses	1									1
37. Christmas	1								1	
Total	28	3	6	6	5	5	4	3	3	11

(h) Year 7

Units	Educational	Social	Spiritual	Church	Worship	Saints	Our behaviour	Feasts	Christ	Old Testament
1. God Creates Adam and Eve	1									1
2. Adam and Eve Disobey God	1									1
3. The Parable of the Prodigal Son		1					1			
4. The Second Coming			1						1	
5. The Daily Services			1		1					
6. Daniel	1									1
7. The Last Supper			1						1	
8. Joseph's Brothers in Egypt	1									1
9. Holy Week			1		1					
10. Easter Sunday			1		1					
11. St John Chrysostom	1					1				
12. The Holy Liturgy			1	1						
13. Our Lord Jesus Heals a Man who was Born Blind	1								1	
14. The Great Flood	1									1

15. Jesus - The True Vine			1						1	
16. Pentecost			1					1		
17. The Feasts in our Church	1							1		
18. The Holy Liturgy - The Service of Prothesis or Proskomidi			1	1						
19. The Meaning of the Proskomidi			1	1						
20. Joshua	1									1
21. Samson	1									1
22. The Holy Liturgy			1	1						
23. The Prophet Elijah	1									1
24. The Parable of the Two House Builders		1					1			
25. The Dormition of the Theotokos	1							1		
26. St Kosmas Aitolos	1					1				
27. The Parable of the Foolish Rich Man		1						1		
28. The Birth of the Holy Mother of God	1						1			
29. The Holy Liturgy			1	1						
30. St John the Theologian	1						1			
31. Esther	1									1
32. The Holy Liturgy - The Confession of our Faith			1	1						
33. Gideon	1									1
34. St Arsenios	1						1			
35. Job	1									1
36. The Holy Liturgy - Holy Communion			1	1						
37. The Parable of the Talents		1						1		
38. St Nicholas, St Spyridon	1						1			
Total	20	4	14	7	3	6	4	3	4	11

APPENDIX D: A PROGRAM OF CHANTING ACROSS THE GRADES

Orthodox Special Religious Education Basic Hymns for Primary

<p>Year 3</p>	<p>Ἅγιος ὁ Θεός, Ἅγιος ἰσχυρός, Ἅγιος ἀθάνατος, ἐλέησον ἡμᾶς</p> <p>Εἶδομεν τὸ φῶς τὸ ἀληθινόν, ἐλάβομεν Πνεῦμα ἐπουράνιον, εὐρομεν πίστιν ἀληθῆ, ἀδιαίρετον Τριάδα προσκυνοῦντες, αὕτη γὰρ ἡμᾶς ἔσωσεν</p> <p>Ὁ Μονογενῆς Υἱὸς καὶ Λόγος τοῦ Θεοῦ, ἀθάνατος ὑπάρχων καὶ καταδεξάμενος διὰ τὴν ἡμετέραν σωτηρίαν σαρκωθῆναι ἐκ τῆς ἁγίας Θεοτόκου καὶ ἀειπαρθένου Μαρίας, ἀτρέπτως ἐνανθρωπήσας, σταυρωθεὶς τε Χριστὲ ὁ Θεός, θανάτῳ θάνατον πατήσας, εἷς ὢν τῆς Ἁγίας Τριάδος, συνδοξαζόμενος τῷ Πατρὶ καὶ τῷ Ἁγίῳ Πνεύματι, σῶσον ἡμᾶς</p>
<p>Year 4</p>	<p>Easter hymn - Χριστὸς ἀνέστη ἐκ νεκρῶν, θανάτῳ θάνατον πατήσας, καὶ τοῖς ἐν τοῖς μνήμασι, ζῶν χαρισάμενος.</p> <p>Ἅγιος, ἅγιος, ἅγιος Κύριος Σαβῶθ πλήρης ὁ οὐρανὸς καὶ ἡ γῆ τῆς δόξης σου, ὡσαννὰ ἐν τοῖς ὑψίστοις. Εὐλογημένος ὁ ἐρχόμενος ἐν ὀνόματι Κυρίου. Ὡσαννὰ ὁ ἐν τοῖς ὑψίστοις</p> <p>Ἄξιόν ἐστιν ὡς ἀληθῶς μακαρίζειν σε τὴν Θεοτόκον, τὴν ἀειμακάριστον καὶ παναμώμητον καὶ μητέρα τοῦ Θεοῦ ἡμῶν. Τὴν τιμιωτέραν τῶν Χερουβείμ καὶ ἐνδοξοτέραν ἀσυγκρίτως τῶν Σεραφείμ· τὴν ἀδιαφθόρως Θεὸν Λόγον τεκοῦσαν, τὴν ὄντως Θεοτόκον, σὲ μεγαλύνομεν</p>
<p>Year 5</p>	<p>Ἡ γέννησίς σου Χριστέ ο Θεός ημῶν, ἀπέτειλε τῷ κόσμῳ τὸ φῶς τὸ τῆς γνώσεως, ἐν αὐτῇ γὰρ οἱ τοῖς ἀστροῖς λατρεύοντες, ὑπο ἀστέρος ἐδιδασκοντο. Σε προσκυνοῦν, τὸν Ἥλιον τῆς δικαιοσύνης καὶ σε γινώσκουν ἐξ ὑψους Ἀνοτολῆν, Κύριε δοξα σοί.</p> <p>Προστασία τῶν Χριστιανῶν ἀκαταίσχυντε, μεσιτεία πρὸς τὸν Ποιητὴν ἀμετάθετε. Μὴ παρίδῃς ἁμαρτωλῶν δεήσεων φωνάς, ἀλλὰ πρόφθασον, ὡς ἀγαθὴ, εἰς τὴν βοήθειαν ἡμῶν, τῶν πιστῶν κραυγαζόντων σοί· Τάχυνον εἰς πρεσβείαν, καὶ σπεῦσον εἰς ἰκεσίαν, ἢ προστατεύουσα ἀεὶ, Θεοτόκε, τῶν τιμώντων σε.</p> <p>Τῇ ὑπερμάχῳ στρατηγῷ τὰ νικητήρια, ὡς λυτρωθεῖσα τῶν δεινῶν εὐχαριστήρια, ἀναγράφω σοὶ ἡ πόλις σου, Θεοτόκε ἀλλ' ὡς ἔχουσα τὸ κράτος ἀπροσμάχητον, ἐκ παντοίων με κινδύνων ἐλευθέρωσον, ἵνα κράζω σοὶ Χαῖρε Νύμφη ἀνύμφευτε.</p>
<p>Year 6</p>	<p>Theophany hymn - Ἐν Ἰορδάνῃ βαπτιζομένου σου Κύριε, ἡ τῆς Τριάδος ἐφανερώθη προσκύνῃς· τοῦ γὰρ Γεννήτορος ἡ φωνὴ προσεμαρτύρει σοί, ἀγαπητὸν σε Υἱὸν ὀνομάζουσα· καὶ τὸ Πνεῦμα ἐν εἶδει περισσεῶς, ἐβεβαίου τοῦ λόγου τὸ ἀσφαλές. Ὁ ἐπιφανεὶς Χριστὲ ὁ Θεός, καὶ τὸν κόσμον φωτίσας δόξα σοί</p> <p>September 14th – Troparion of the Holy Cross Σῶσον Κύριε τὸ λαόν σου, καὶ εὐλόγησον τὴν κληρονομίαν σου</p> <p>August 15th – Apolytikion of the Dormition of the Theotokos</p>

	Εν τη γεννήσει την παρθενίαν εφύλαξας...
Year7	<p>March 25th – Apolytikion of the Annunciation Σήμεραρον της σωτηρίας ημών το κεφάλαιον...</p> <p>August 6th – Apolytikion of the Transfiguration Μετεμορφώθης εν τω όρει Χριστέ ο Θεος....</p> <p>Πλούσιοι έπτώχευσαν και έπέινασαν...</p> <p>.</p>

E&OE; Draft listing – to be updated